

Synthesis, Structural, Photocatalytic Activity of Ni-Nd-Co Nano Ferrites Synthesized by Citrate Gel Auto Combustion Method

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Abstract: Using the citrate gel method, nanostructured ferrites with the formula $Ni_xNd_yCo_{1-x}Fe_{2-y}O_4$ (where $x=y=0.00$ to 0.5 with 0.1 variation) were synthesized in order to study their structural, morphological, and photocatalytic activity. A cubic spinel structure with crystallite diameters between 14.62 to 32.24 nm was established by X-ray diffraction (XRD). The lattice parameter and unit cell volume also decreased with increased doping, while X-ray density increased due to the incorporation of heavier Nd^{3+} ions. The microstructure confirmed successful nanoscale synthesis. Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS) analysis verified the presence of all intended elements (Fe, Co, Ni, Nd, O), confirming compositional integrity. Molecular vibrations were described by Raman spectroscopy, which verified the production of spinel structures. The most intense peak in the Raman spectrum typically appears around 678 cm^{-1} , attributed to the A_{1g} mode corresponding to symmetric stretching of Fe–O bonds in the tetrahedral sites. Photocatalytic activity of the nano ferrites investigated with two organic dyes like methylene blue and acid red irradiated by visible light.

Key words: Citrate gel auto combustion method, XRD, FE-SEM, Raman, photocatalytic activity.

1. INTRODUCTION

AB_2O_4 ferrites are a class of magnetic materials with the general formula AB_2O_4 , where A and B are metal ions. These ferrites exhibit a variety of magnetic properties, making them useful in applications such as magnetic recording, antennas, and sensors. Their structure consists of spinel crystals, where A ions occupy tetrahedral sites and B ions occupy octahedral sites. Nano ferrites are ferrimagnetic materials composed of iron oxides combined with other metal ions like nickel, zinc, or cobalt at the nanoscale[1,2]. Their crystal structure allows unequal magnetic moments in different sublattices to align oppositely, resulting in net magnetization. Due to their small size (1–100 nm), they exhibit enhanced surface area, super para magnetism, and low coercivity. These properties make them useful in high-frequency devices, magnetic storage, biomedical imaging, and drug delivery. The ferrimagnetism in nano ferrites is due to strong exchange interactions between ions at tetrahedral and octahedral sites, leading to unique magnetic behaviour not seen in bulk counterparts[3,4].

Nano ferrites can be synthesized using various methods that influence their structural and magnetic properties. Common preparation techniques include the sol-gel method, co-precipitation, hydrothermal or solvothermal synthesis, and microwave-assisted synthesis. Other widely used methods are combustion synthesis, ball milling, spray pyrolysis, thermal decomposition, and microemulsion[5–8]. The sol-gel method offers several advantages in the synthesis of nano ferrites. One of the main benefits is its low processing temperature, which helps preserve the nanoscale structure and prevents unwanted grain growth. This method ensures homogeneous mixing of metal ions at the molecular level, resulting in uniform chemical composition throughout the material. It also provides excellent control over particle size and morphology, which is crucial for optimizing the magnetic properties of nano ferrites. Additionally, the sol-gel process produces high-purity products due to minimal contamination and is versatile enough to create various forms such as powders, coatings, and thin films. Moreover, it is cost-effective and uses relatively simple equipment and inexpensive precursors, making it suitable for both laboratory and industrial-scale production. Nano ferrites play a significant role in wastewater treatment due to their unique magnetic, chemical, and surface properties. These materials can adsorb and degrade various pollutants, including heavy metals, dyes, and organic contaminants. Their high surface area enhances the adsorption capacity, while the presence of metal ions (like Fe, Ni, Co, or Zn) allows for catalytic activity. One key advantage of nano ferrites is their magnetic separability after treating wastewater, they can be easily removed using an external magnetic field, preventing secondary pollution and enabling reusability. They also serve as effective catalysts in photocatalysis and electrocatalysis, helping break down toxic compounds into less harmful substances[9–12]. Thus, nano ferrites are emerging as efficient, reusable, and eco-friendly materials for sustainable wastewater purification technologies.

In this current study we synthesized $Ni_xNd_yCo_{1-x}Fe_{2-y}O_4$ (where $x=y=0.00$ to 0.5 with 0.1 variation) nano ferrites by citrate gel method. synthesized materials investigated structural, morphological, and photocatalytic activity.

2. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

2.1 Synthesis of Ni-Nd-Co nano ferrites

$\text{Ni}_x\text{Nd}_y\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_{2-y}\text{O}_4$ (where $x=y=0.00$ to 0.5 with 0.1 variation) nano ferrites were synthesized by citrate gel auto combustion method. The citrate gel method is a widely used technique for synthesizing nano ferrites due to its simplicity and effectiveness in producing fine, homogeneous powders. In this method, metal nitrates (such as iron nitrate and other metal salts) are dissolved in distilled water. Citric acid is added as a chelating agent to form stable metal-citrate complexes, ensuring uniform distribution of metal ions. The pH of the solution is adjusted using ammonia, which helps in the gelation process. The solution is then heated and continuously stirred until it forms a viscous gel. Upon further heating, the viscous gel dries to form a dry gel, which is then ignited or heated to form a brown-coloured precursor powder. This powder is sintered at 500°C to improve crystallinity and remove residual organic materials[13,14]. Finally, the sintered material is ground for one hour to obtain a fine nano-sized ferrite powder suitable for various applications. The brief synthesis procedure of the citrate gel auto combustion method is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig.1 Schematic Synthesis of Ni-Nd-Co nano ferrites.

2.2 Characterization of samples

To determine the spinel-phase and cubic character of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Nd}_y\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_{2-y}\text{O}_4$ (where $x=y=0.00$ to 0.5 with 0.1 variation) nanoparticles, X-ray diffraction was performed using a Bruker D-8 advanced and an X-ray diffractometer with $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation at 0.15406 nm. Energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) (JEOL JSM-6480LV) and a Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FE-SEM, JEOL JSM-6480LV) were used to analyze the morphology. The degradation of MB was measured using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (UVS-2800, USA), and the absorbance of the irradiated mixture was measured at various time intervals.

2.3 Photocatalytic Activity

Two dyes, Acid-Red and Methylene-Blue, which were reflected by visible light, carried out the photocatalytic activity of the synthesized samples. The experiment involved the preparation of 0.05g of MB and AR, as well as the separate dissolution of 0.05g of catalysts (ferrite sample) in DD water. The catalyst and weighted dye were dissolved in around 50 millilitres of DD water, and the mixture was thoroughly mixed with a magnetic stirrer before being left in the dark for about 20 minutes. About 30 to 40 centimetres separate the tubes from the 400 W power bulb utilized in this experiment. A 20 -gauge syringe was used to take the irradiation samples at pre-arranged intervals of time, in this case fixed at 15 minutes.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 X-ray diffraction Studies of Ni-Nd-Co nano ferrites

X-ray Diffraction (XRD) plays a crucial role in the characterization of nano ferrites. It provides essential information about the crystalline structure, phase purity, and crystallite size of the synthesized material. XRD confirms the formation of the desired spinel structure, which is typical of most ferrites. By analysing the diffraction peaks, researchers can identify the specific ferrite phase and detect any unwanted secondary phases or impurities[15,16]. Fig.2 shows the XRD pattern of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Nd}_y\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_{2-y}\text{O}_4$ (where $x=y=0.00$ to 0.5 with 0.1 variation) nano ferrites.

The X-ray Diffraction (XRD) analysis of Ni-Nd-Co nano ferrites typically reveals the formation of a single-phase cubic spinel structure. The diffraction peaks correspond to standard planes such as (220), (311), (400), (422), (511), and (440), confirming the crystalline nature of the material. The observed patterns match well with the JCPDS card (22-1086) of cubic spinel ferrites, indicating high phase purity. The structure belongs to the face-centered cubic (FCC) system with the $Fd\bar{3}m$ space group, which is characteristic of spinel ferrites. The absence of extra peaks in the XRD pattern confirms that no secondary phases are present, indicating successful synthesis of pure Ni-Nd-Co nano ferrites[17,18]. The following Debye-Scherrer formula have been used to calculate the crystalline size of the Ni-Nd-Co nano ferrites.

$$\text{Crystalline size } (l) = \frac{0.94\lambda}{\beta \cos\theta} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where λ is the wavelength β is the full width half maxima, and θ is the brags angle.

Fig.2 XRD pattern of $Ni_xNd_yCo_{1-x}Fe_{2-y}O_4$ (where $x=y=0.00$ to 0.5 with 0.1 variation) nano ferrites

The crystalline size of the materials shows a significant decreasing trend with increasing substitution of Co^{2+} by Ni^{2+} and Nd^{3+} ions. The undoped $CoFe_2O_4$ has the largest crystalline size of 32.24 nm. upon doping with Ni and Nd metals crystalline size decreasing from 32 nm to 14 nm. The smallest size recorded is 14.62 nm for $Co_{0.5}Ni_{0.5}Nd_{0.5}Fe_2O_4$. This reduction in crystallite size can be attributed to the lattice strain introduced by the ionic size mismatch and local structural distortions caused by the dopant ions. These effects tend to suppress crystal growth, leading to the formation of smaller nanoparticles. Crystalline size and lattice parameter of $Ni_xNd_yCo_{1-x}Fe_{2-y}O_4$ (where $x=y=0.00$ to 0.5 with 0.1 variation) nano ferrites indicated in **Fig. 3**. The synthesized Ni-Nd-Co Nano ferrites lattice constant were calculated by following formula.

$$\text{Lattice parameter } (a) = d\sqrt{h^2 + k^2 + k^2} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where d attributed the interplanar distance and hkl attributed the miller indices.

The lattice parameter also exhibits a decreasing trend with increasing doping. The value drops from 8.356 Å for pure CoFe_2O_4 to 8.301 Å for the highest doped composition. This reduction indicates that Ni^{2+} (ionic radius 0.69 Å) and Nd^{3+} (0.98 Å) ions influence the unit cell dimensions when they substitute for Co^{2+} (0.74 Å). Although Nd^{3+} is larger, the combined effect with smaller Ni^{2+} and possible redistribution of cations in tetrahedral and octahedral sites contributes to the overall contraction of the lattice. The volume of unit cell of the materials has been calculated by the following equation.

$$\text{Volume of unit cell } V = a^3 \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Where a indicates the lattice parameter of the materials.

Fig. 4 illustrates the volume of unit cell and X-ray density of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Nd}_y\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_{2-y}\text{O}_4$ (where $x=y=0.00$ to 0.5 with 0.1 variation) nano ferrites. The volume of the unit cell shows a decreasing trend with increasing Ni and Nd doping. The undoped CoFe_2O_4 has the highest unit cell volume of 583.470 Å, which gradually decreases to 571.993 Å for the $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Nd}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_{1.5}\text{O}_4$ sample. This reduction is consistent with the decrease in lattice parameter, as the unit cell volume is directly related to the cube of the lattice constant [19,20]. The materials X-ray density were calculated by following equation.

$$\text{X-ray density } d_x = \frac{ZM}{Na^3} \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Where Z indicates the no of molecules (8), " a " is the lattice parameter, " M " corresponds to the composition molecular weight, and " N " corresponds the Avogadro number. The X-ray density increases gradually from 5.340 gm/cm^3 (CoFe_2O_4) to 6.432 gm/cm^3 . This increase can be attributed to the replacement of Co^{2+} ions by heavier Nd^{3+} ions, which raises the overall atomic mass.

Table 1 $\text{Ni}_x\text{Nd}_y\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_{2-y}\text{O}_4$ (where $x=y=0.00$ to 0.5 with 0.1 variation) nano ferrites.

Name of the composition	2θ	Crystalline size (nm)	Lattice parameter (Å)	Volume of unit cell (Å)	X-ray density (gm/cm^3)
CoFe_2O_4	35.547	32.24	8.356	583.470	5.340
$\text{Co}_{0.9}\text{Ni}_{0.1}\text{Nd}_{0.1}\text{Fe}_{1.9}\text{O}_4$	35.766	18.304	8.342	580.511	5.640
$\text{Co}_{0.8}\text{Ni}_{0.2}\text{Nd}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{1.8}\text{O}_4$	35.653	15.878	8.331	578.339	5.793
$\text{Co}_{0.7}\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Nd}_{0.3}\text{Fe}_{1.7}\text{O}_4$	35.691	15.093	8.323	576.642	6.105
$\text{Co}_{0.6}\text{Ni}_{0.4}\text{Nd}_{0.4}\text{Fe}_{1.6}\text{O}_4$	35.760	14.673	8.307	573.267	6.253
$\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Nd}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_{1.5}\text{O}_4$	35.710	14.622	8.301	571.993	6.432

3.2 SEM Studies of Ni-Nd-Co nano ferrites.

Fig 5 (a-f) shows the SEM (Scanning Electron Microscopy) images of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Nd}_y\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_{2-y}\text{O}_4$ (where $x=y=0.00$ to 0.5 with 0.1 variation) nano ferrites, provide detailed insight into the surface morphology and microstructure of the synthesized material. The images clearly show the presence of well-developed grains with distinct grain boundaries, indicating a good degree of crystallinity and uniform sintering. The grains are mostly circular to nearly spherical in shape, which is a typical characteristic of ferrites synthesized via chemical routes such as the citrate gel method. Some degree of agglomeration is observed, which is expected in nano-sized materials due to their high surface-to-volume ratio, magnetic dipole interactions, and Vander Waals forces [21,22]. This agglomeration often occurs during the drying and calcination stages. However, even within agglomerated clusters, individual grains are visible and fairly uniform in size. The microstructure observed in SEM supports the successful synthesis of nano-scale Ni-Nd-Co, which is advantageous for various applications including magnetic devices, catalysis, and wastewater treatment due to their enhanced surface area, magnetic response, and chemical activity.

Fig. 5 SEM images of $Ni_xNd_yCo_{1-x}Fe_{2-y}O_4$ (where $x=y=0.00$ to 0.5 with 0.1 variation) nano ferrites

EDS is a crucial analytical technique used for elemental analysis and chemical characterization of nano ferrites. It is especially valuable for confirming the successful synthesis of compounds, detecting impurities, and understanding the microstructure composition relationship in advanced materials. **Fig. 6** indicates the EDS spectra of $Ni_xNd_yCo_{1-x}Fe_{2-y}O_4$ (where $x=y=0.00$ to 0.5 with 0.1 variation) nano ferrites. The Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS) analysis confirms the presence of Oxygen (O), Iron (Fe), Cobalt (Co), Nickel (Ni), and Neodymium (Nd) in both samples. The spectra reveal that iron is the most abundant element, followed by varying amounts of cobalt and neodymium, with nickel present in smaller quantities. The quantitative results indicate that the upper sample contains a higher amount of iron and cobalt, while the lower sample shows a relatively increased content of neodymium and nickel. These differences suggest slight compositional variations between these samples, potentially influencing their structural or functional properties.

Fig. 6 EDS graphs of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Nd}_y\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_{2-y}\text{O}_4$ (where $x=y=0.00,0.3,0.5,0.6$) nano ferrites

3.3 Raman spectrum of Ni-Nd-Co nano ferrites

The Raman spectrum gives the valuable insights into their crystal structure, cation distribution, and vibrational properties. **Fig 7** indicates the Raman spectrum of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Nd}_y\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_{2-y}\text{O}_4$ (where $x=y=0.00$ to 0.5 with 0.1 variation) nano ferrites. These ferrites crystallize in a cubic spinel structure with the general formula AB_2O_4 , where Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ions occupy the tetrahedral (A) and octahedral (B) sites along with Fe^{3+} ions. Raman spectroscopy is particularly useful for characterizing such ferrites at the nanoscale, as it reveals vibrational modes associated with the metal–oxygen bonds in the spinel lattice. The ideal spinel structure, with space group $\text{Fd}3\text{m}$ exhibits five Raman-active vibrational modes: $\text{A}_{1\text{g}}$, E_{g} and three $\text{T}_{2\text{g}}$ modes[23]. The most intense peak in the Raman spectrum typically appears around 678 cm^{-1} , attributed to the $\text{A}_{1\text{g}}$ mode corresponding to symmetric stretching of Fe–O bonds in the tetrahedral sites. Other significant peaks include modes around 566 cm^{-1} ($\text{T}_{2\text{g}}$ (3)), 448 cm^{-1} ($\text{T}_{2\text{g}}$ (2)), 366 cm^{-1} (E_{g}), and 275 cm^{-1} ($\text{T}_{2\text{g}}$ (1)), each associated with different bending or stretching vibrations involving Fe–O–Fe linkages in tetrahedral and octahedral environments. Variations in the Ni and Nd content affect both the position and intensity of these peaks, as the ionic radii and site preferences of Ni^{2+} and Nd^{3+} influence the local lattice dynamics. Ni^{2+} ions tend to prefer tetrahedral sites, while Nd^{3+} ions favour octahedral coordination, altering the Fe^{3+} distribution and hence the Raman activity. In nanoscale ferrites, peak broadening and slight shifts are often observed due to quantum confinement effects and lattice strain. Additionally, increased crystallite size and improved crystallinity through thermal treatment lead to sharper and more defined Raman peaks.

Fig. 7 Raman spectrum of Ni_xNd_yCo_{1-x}Fe_{2-y}O₄ (where x=y=0.00 to 0.5 with 0.1 variation) nano ferrites

3.4 Photocatalytic Activity

3.4.1 Photocatalytic activity of methylene blue

Photocatalytic activity plays a vital role in environmental remediation, particularly in the degradation of harmful organic dyes like methylene blue (MB), a widely used cationic dye in textiles, paper, and pharmaceuticals. MB is toxic, non-biodegradable, and stable in water, posing serious health and ecological risks if released into natural water bodies. Fig. 8 illustrates the photocatalytic degradation of methylene blue (MB) under visible light using Ni_xNd_yCo_{1-x}Fe_{2-y}O₄ (where x=y=0.00, 0.1,0.3and 0.5) nano ferrites. All spectra display a characteristic MB absorbance peak around 650 nm, attributed to the π-π transition[24,25]. Upon visible light irradiation, a progressive decline in peak intensity is observed over time (15–90 minutes), indicating effective dye degradation. The photocatalytic degradation efficiency of the synthesized nanomaterials was evaluated using the following formula:

$$\text{Degradation efficiency (\%)} = \frac{C}{C_0} \times 100 \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

In this equation, C₀ represents the initial concentration of methylene blue (MB), while C refers to the concentration of the dye at a given time interval during visible light irradiation. This calculation provides a quantitative measure of the photocatalytic performance of the nanoferrites in degrading organic pollutants from aqueous solutions. The synthesized Ni_xNd_yCo_{1-x}Fe_{2-y}O₄ (where x=y=0.00, 0.1,0.3and 0.5) nano ferrites were tested for their efficiency in degrading methylene blue under visible light exposure, illustrated in Fig 9. Among the tested compositions, undoped CoFe₂O₄ exhibits the highest degradation efficiency (~57%) after 90 minutes, highlighting its strong semiconducting nature and effective visible-light responsiveness. Doped samples show varying performance: Co_{0.9}Ni_{0.1}Nd_{0.1}Fe_{2.0}O₄ and Co_{0.7}Ni_{0.3}Nd_{0.3}Fe_{2.0}O₄ achieve moderate efficiencies (~35–40%), while Co_{0.5}Ni_{0.5}Nd_{0.5}Fe_{2.0}O₄ shows a significant improvement (~50%), nearly matching that of pure CoFe₂O₄. The improved efficiency at higher doping levels can be attributed to enhanced visible-light absorption and better charge carrier separation due to band gap narrowing and lattice modifications introduced by Ni²⁺ and Nd³⁺.

Fig. 8 Photocatalytic activity of methylene blue of $Ni_xNd_yCo_{1-x}Fe_{2-y}O_4$ (where $x=y=0.00, 0.1, 0.3$ and 0.5) nano ferrites

Fig. 9 Photocatalytic degradation efficiency of methylene blue of $Ni_xNd_yCo_{1-x}Fe_{2-y}O_4$ (where $x=y=0.00, 0.1, 0.3$ and 0.5) nano ferrites

Fig. 11 Photocatalytic degradation efficiency of acid red of $Ni_xNd_yCo_{1-x}Fe_{2-y}O_4$ (where $x=y=0.00, 0.1, 0.3$ and 0.5) nano ferrites

3.4.2 Photocatalytic activity of acid red

Photocatalysis is a promising, sustainable approach for environmental remediation, especially in eliminating toxic, non-biodegradable organic dyes from industrial effluents. Acid red is an anionic azo dye, hazardous, often used in textile and food industries. The present study evaluates the photocatalytic degradation of acid red under visible light $Ni_xNd_yCo_{1-x}Fe_{2-y}O_4$ nano ferrites with varying dopant concentrations ($x=y=0.00, 0.1, 0.3$ and 0.5) as shown in **Fig. 10**. The degradation performance was quantitatively assessed using the standard degradation efficiency equation 5. Each spectrum in Fig. 4 shows a prominent absorbance peak around 510–520 nm, characteristic of acid red. Upon visible light irradiation, there is a progressive decline in absorbance over time (15–90 minutes), confirming effective photocatalytic activity.

The photocatalytic degradation efficiency of acid red (AR) dye using $Ni_xNd_yCo_{1-x}Fe_{2-y}O_4$ nano ferrites with varying dopant concentrations ($x=y=0.00, 0.1, 0.3$ and 0.5) nano ferrites is illustrated in **Fig. 11**. The degradation performance of the undoped cobalt ferrite ($CoFe_2O_4$) is relatively poor, reaching only about 15% after 90 minutes of irradiation. However, with the incorporation of Ni^{2+} and Nd^{3+} ions into the spinel ferrite structure, a significant improvement in photocatalytic efficiency is observed. Among the doped samples, $Co_{0.7}Ni_{0.3}Nd_{0.3}Fe_{1.7}O_4$ exhibits the highest photocatalytic activity, achieving around 55% degradation efficiency within 90 minutes.

The sample with lower doping concentration $Co_{0.9}Ni_{0.1}Nd_{0.1}Fe_{1.9}O_4$ shows moderate performance (~35%), indicating that minimal substitution provides some improvement over the pure ferrite but is less effective than higher doping levels. Meanwhile, the heavily doped sample $Co_{0.5}Ni_{0.5}Nd_{0.5}Fe_{1.5}O_4$ shows slightly lower efficiency (~45%) compared to the optimally doped one, possibly due to excessive lattice distortion or the formation of recombination centres that counteract the benefits of doping. These results suggest that a balanced substitution level, specifically at $x = y = 0.3$, provides the best combination of structural and electronic properties for enhanced photocatalytic degradation of AR. This enhanced activity is attributed to the optimal doping concentration, which improves charge separation, reduces electron-hole recombination, and increases the number of active sites for dye degradation.

Fig. 10 Photocatalytic activity of acid red of $\text{Ni}_x\text{Nd}_y\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_{2-y}\text{O}_4$ (where $x=y=0.00, 0.1, 0.3$ and 0.5) nano ferrites

4. CONCLUSIONS

$\text{Ni}_x\text{Nd}_y\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_{2-y}\text{O}_4$ (where $x=y=0.00, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4$ and 0.5) nano ferrites synthesized by citrate gel auto combustion method successfully. X-ray diffraction (XRD) confirmed the formation of a single-phase cubic spinel structure with high crystallinity and phase purity. Doping with Ni^{2+} and Nd^{3+} resulted in a decrease in crystallite size from 32.24 nm to 14 nm. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) images revealed uniform, nearly spherical grains with some agglomeration a common feature in nano-sized materials. Raman spectra provided insight into the vibrational modes and cation distribution in the spinel lattice. The main A_{1g} peak at 678 cm^{-1} corresponded to Fe–O symmetric stretching in tetrahedral sites. Photocatalytic experiments showed that undoped CoFe_2O_4 exhibited the highest efficiency (57%) in degrading methylene blue under visible light. In contrast, for acid red degradation, undoped CoFe_2O_4 showed poor performance (15%), while the optimally doped $\text{Co}_{0.7}\text{Ni}_{0.3}\text{Nd}_{0.3}\text{Fe}_{1.7}\text{O}_4$ achieved the highest degradation efficiency (~55%). Lower and higher doping levels showed moderate activity, indicating that an optimal balance of Ni and Nd substitution is critical for maximizing photocatalytic performance in this case. Structural refinement, enhanced charge separation, and tailored optical properties make these nanomaterials promising candidates for visible-light-driven photocatalysis.

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REFERENCES

- [1]. Kershi RM (2021) Redistribution cations at sites of cadmium ferrite nanostructures as a result of Fe^{2+} and Co^{2+} ions dual additions and their magnetic, dielectric, spectroscopic, and mechanical properties. *Mater Chem Phys* 270: 124862.
- [2]. Abdo MA, Al-Wafi R, AlHammad MS (2023) Highly efficient visible light driven photocatalytic activity of rare earth cerium doped zinc-manganese ferrite: Rhodamine B degradation and stability assessment. *Ceram Int* 49: 29245–29258.
- [3]. Farouk E, Mahmoud KR, Hemeda OM, et al. (2024) Interplay Between Structural and Magnetic Properties and Positron Annihilation Studies for Mn-Zn Nano-Ferrites. *J Electron Mater* 53: 1738–1751.

- [4]. Akurati RR, Jaladi NK, Rao KS, et al. (2025) Influence of Copper on Structure, Magnetic Properties, and Magnetic Induction Heating Response in Co–Cu Nanoferrites. *J Supercond Nov Magn* 38: 95.
- [5]. Basfer NM, Al-Harbi N (2023) Structural, optical and photocatalytic activity of Ce³⁺ doped Co–Mg nanoparticles for wastewater treatment applications. *J King Saud Univ Sci* 35: 102436.
- [6]. Kumar NH, Venkateshwarlu J, Latha M, et al. (2025) Effect of Rare Earth Gd³⁺ Doping on the Structural, Magnetic and Optical Properties Co–Cd Spinel Nanoferrites. *Semiconductors* 59: 139–148.
- [7]. Asogekar PA, Gaonkar SK, Kumar A, et al. (2021) Influence of Co over magnetically benign Zn ferrite system and study of its structural, dielectric, superparamagnetic and antibacterial efficacy. *Mater Res Bull* 141: 111330.
- [8]. Irfan M, Ayyaz M, Naz MY, et al. (2022) Testing of optical, dielectric and photocatalytic properties of Ce³⁺ doped cobalt–cadmium nanocomposite for high frequency devices and wastewater treatment. *Ceram Int* 48: 8517–8528.
- [9]. Nasr MH, Elkholy MM, El-Deen LMS, et al. (2024) Synthesis, structural, electrical and magnetic characteristics of Co–Cd spinel nano ferrites synthesized via sol-gel auto combustion method. *J Solgel Sci Technol*.
- [10]. Basfer NM, Al-Harbi N (2023) Structural, optical and photocatalytic activity of Ce³⁺ doped Co–Mg nanoparticles for wastewater treatment applications. *J King Saud Univ Sci* 35: 102436.
- [11]. Jasrotia R, Suman, Verma A, et al. (2022) Photocatalytic dye degradation efficiency and reusability of Cu-substituted Zn–Mg spinel nanoferrites for wastewater remediation. *Journal of Water Process Engineering* 48: 102865.
- [12]. Fouda A, Eid AM, Abdelkareem A, et al. (2022) Phyco-Synthesized Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles Using Marine Macroalgae, *Ulva fasciata* Delile, Characterization, Antibacterial Activity, Photocatalysis, and Tanning Wastewater Treatment. *Catalysts* 12: 756.
- [13]. Bhabala AK, Kumar DR, Ahmad SI, et al. (2023) Optical, luminescence and photocatalytic activity of Sr based Mg, Ce nano ferrites synthesized by citrate gel auto combustion method, *Materials Today: Proceedings*.
- [14]. Mahipal B, Venkatesh N, Kumar DR, et al. (2023) Structural, optical, magnetic and dielectric properties of Ag doped Mg nano ferrites prepared by citrate gel auto combustion method. *J Mol Struct* 1277.
- [15]. Jain R (2022) A Review on the Development of XRD in Ferrite Nanoparticles. *J Supercond Nov Magn* 35.
- [16]. Deepty M, Srinivas C, Kumar ER, et al. (2019) XRD, EDX, FTIR and ESR spectroscopic studies of co-precipitated Mn–substituted Zn–ferrite nanoparticles. *Ceram Int* 45.
- [17]. Ghorbani H, Eshraghi M, Sabouri Dodaran AA (2022) Structural and magnetic properties of cobalt ferrite nanoparticles doped with cadmium. *Physica B Condens Matter* 634: 413816.
- [18]. Bardapurkar PP, Dalvi SN, Joshi VD, et al. (2022) Effect of silica matrix on structural and optical properties of cobalt ferrite nanoparticles. *Results in Surfaces and Interfaces* 8.
- [19]. Aisida SO, Ugwu K, Agbogu A, et al. (2023) Synthesis of intrinsic, Manganese and magnesium doped cobalt ferrite nanoparticles: Physical properties for antibacterial activities. *Hybrid Advances* 3: 100049.
- [20]. Ahmad SI, Suresh MB, Kumar DR (2019) Structural, morphological, dielectric and room-temperature magnetic studies of Ce³⁺ substituted nano crystalline cobalt ferrite, *AIP Conference Proceedings*.
- [21]. Thankachan S, Femsy M V., John N (2020) Influence of silver doping on the structural properties of magnesium ferrite nanoparticles and its possible antibacterial activity. *Mater Today Proc* 25: 289–293.
- [22]. Aji Udhaya P, Bessy TC, Meena M (2019) Antibacterial activity of nickel and magnesium substituted ferrite nanoparticles synthesized via self-combustion method. *Mater Today Proc* 8: 169–175.
- [23]. Cherpil C, Lister D, Dacquait F, et al. (2021) Study of the solid-state synthesis of nickel ferrite (NiFe₂O₄) by X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and raman spectroscopy. *Materials* 14.
- [24]. Bhukal S, Bansal S, Singhal S (2014) Co_{0.6}Zn_{0.4}Cu_{0.2}Cd_xFe_{1.8-x}O₄ (0.2 ≤ x ≤ 0.8) magnetic ferrite nano-particle: Synthesis, characterization and photo-catalytic degradation of methyl orange. *J Mol Struct* 1059: 150–158.
- [25]. Javed M, Akbar N, Khan AA, et al. (2023) Photocatalytic activity of sol-gel self-combustion derived MCr₂O₄ (M= Mg, Ni) spinel chromites for photodegradation of organic dyes. *Mater Today Commun* 35: 105716.
- [26]. Kumari S, Dhanda N, Thakur A, et al. (2023) Nano Ca–Mg–Zn ferrites as tuneable photocatalyst for UV light-induced degradation of rhodamine B dye and antimicrobial behavior for water purification. *Ceram Int* 49: 12469–12480.
- [27]. George M, Ajeesha TL, Manikandan A, et al. (2021) Evaluation of Cu–MgFe₂O₄ spinel nanoparticles for photocatalytic and antimicrobial activities. *Journal of Physics and Chemistry of Solids* 153: 110010.

- [28]. Casbeer E, Sharma VK, Li XZ (2012) Synthesis and photocatalytic activity of ferrites under visible light: A review. *Sep Purif Technol* 87: 1–14.